

Thermal and Optical Properties of Cadmium Manganese Oxalate Crystal Grown by Agar - Agar Gel Method

¹A. A. Gayakwad, ²S. J. Nandre, ³H. S. Pawar and ⁴R. R. Ahire

¹R.C. Patel Anu. Higher Secondary Ashramschoool, Shirpur, (Dhule) M.S.

²Department of Physics, Uttamrao Patil Arts and Science College, Dahiwel, (Dhule) M.S.

³V.J.N.T. Late Dalpatbhau Rathod Junior College, Mordadtanda, (Dhule) M.S.

⁴Department of Physics S.G. Patil Arts, Commerce and Science College, Sakri (Dhule) M.S.

Abstract—Cadmium Manganese oxalate single crystals emerged by the gel technique at room temperature using agar-agar gel media. Ideal growth conditions of cadmium manganese were determined by adjusting gel parameters such supernatant concentration, aging time, gel percentage, and reversal reaction. Nucleation was regulated and the necessary conditions for established morphology of grown crystals were discovered using such a variable. The thermal characteristics of the crystals were examined using TGA, DTA, and DSC. The PL has measured fluoresces properties of grown crystal.

Keywords —Agar-Agar Gel Technique, TGA, DTA, DSC, PL.

I. INTRODUCTION

A solid substance with atoms, ions, or molecules arranged in a highly ordered, three-dimensional design is called a crystal. The crystal has an identifiable form and set of characteristics because of the repetition of this arrangement. The process by which crystals develop from a solution is known as crystal growth. Investigation on crystal growth is currently expanding quickly due to the high demand for crystals in many different fields, including ceramics, physics, chemistry, metallurgy, mineralogy, medicine, engineering, and semiconductors, amplifiers, optics, piezoelectric, photosensitive materials, infrared, nonlinear optics, microelectronics, and microprocessors [1-3]. Some of the best techniques for growing crystals is the gel method. Because the technique's underlying premise is so easy to understand. It is a very easy and simple technique that allows for flawless and stress-free crystal development. Numerous crystals can be produced in an easy and affordable manner. Using the gel technique, insoluble or sparingly soluble crystals were created. In the gel procedures, a solution of two appropriate chemicals that, through a straightforward reaction, produce the necessary insoluble crystalline substance permits a chemical reaction in the designated gel medium. When it comes to growing crystals at room temperature, the gel method is the simplest and easily modified methodology [4]. Since metal oxalate and transition metal oxalates are soluble in water, producing single crystals in gels is a great and easy method [5-7].

Agar-agar gel is superior gel-forming qualities, clarity, and low toxicity make it a popular choice for crystal formation research. Agar-agar gel is used in very few studies to form crystals [8-10], while silica gel is used in many studies [11- 16]. The gel method has occasionally employed to investigate the crystal formation of cadmium manganese oxalate [17]. Cadmium Manganese oxalate is a highly intriguing chemical due to its numerous applications. Therefore, it has been chosen to use the agar-agar gel method to produce and analyse cadmium manganese oxalate crystal throughout the current experiment. The properties of crystals of cadmium manganese oxalate that were generated using different methods are described.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A 250ml glass beaker and a single glass tube measuring 15cm and 2.5cm in diameter have been cleaned with acetone and rinsed with double-distilled water to eliminate any remaining organic and inorganic moisture. Agar-agar powder, oxalic acid ($H_2C_2O_4$), and mix cadmium manganese chloride ($CdMnCl_2$) were employed as chemical compounds of AR grade. To achieve the appropriate volume and morality, the test tube was stuffed by an oxalic acid solution of the appropriate volume and morality. Agar powder (0.5g to 2.5g) was mixed with 100mL of boiling water to create the gel. The heated agar-agar gel was then transferred into a test tube and allowed to solidify. The second reactant as a mixture containing the same ratio of manganese chloride and cadmium chloride in single diffusion was placed on top of the gel after it had set and aged. The tube's open end was sealed with cotton plugs and maintained at room

temperature. The test tube's interface showed some nucleation after six to seven days, and the different shaped crystals that had developed there were subsequently removed from the gel. As the crystals grew, they were gathered and examined. The process that drives the crystal of cadmium manganese oxalate to develop was described as

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To create the ideal environment for crystal growth. It was found that the manganese oxalate crystal was developing in a test tube. The impact of various gel parameters, such as reactant concentration, gel percentage, reverse reactant, gel setting, and aging time, was examined. Mix Cadmium Manganese chloride concentration shifts from 0.2M to 2.5M while other parameters, including oxalic acid concentration, gel percentage, gel setting, and aging time, remain steady at ambient temperature. In the test tube, controlled development nucleation was perceived. As seen in figure 1, growth crystals of higher quality were produced at 1M compared to other concentrations. Growth crystals are seen build up on the gel's surface as the concentration rises and their quantity falls.

Fig.1. Impact on growth of cadmium manganese oxalate crystal in different concentration of cadmium manganese chloride

Fig. 2. Quadrilateral, diamond and cubic in morphology of grown cadmium manganese oxalate crystal.

To examine how different percentages gel, affect the development of cadmium manganese oxalate crystals. At room temperature, gel percentages were reduced from 0.5% to 2% while other gel parameters remained unchanged. It was discovered that while the quantity of crystal beads rose as the agar gel

percentage rose, the shine of the crystals diminished. Agar gel at 1% yields superior results to other types. Nucleation was shown to be easily initiated at the interlayer and inside the test tube over the 36-hour aging period [18]. Good quality of cadmium manganese oxalate crystals with a different of morphologies observed such as quadrilateral, rhombus, cubic, kite like shape, granular, spheroidal, and white in colour. The formation of cadmium manganese oxalate crystals in the test tube is depicted in figure 1 and the different shapes of cadmium manganese oxalate crystals exhibit in figure 2.

III. CHARACTERIZATION

A. THERMOGRAVIMETRY ANALYSIS (TGA)

Recrystallized alumina sample holder was used and the heating rate was $10^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Thermograms were recorded in the temperature range from 30°C to 900°C . The sample was heated from 30°C to 900°C at $100^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ after being held for 1.0min at 300°C to evaporate any remaining moisture. Cadmium Manganese oxalate crystal powder under nitrogen atmosphere was taken as sample at National Chemical Laboratory, Pune for thermal studied. The sample weight for TGA and DTA was 17.763mg. Thermogravimetric analysis is used to measure the thermal stability of the formed crystal and the quantity of water molecules present. The TGA curve for cadmium manganese oxalate crystal is displayed in figure 3. According to the cadmium manganese oxalate thermogram, the compound is stable up to 50°C , and a weight loss of 4.20 % may be the result of water molecules dehydrating between 56°C and 95°C . The weight loss in the range almost matches the calculated weight loss of 4.90%, and the decomposition process continues in this way. The subsequent stage showed a weight loss of 15.83% in the temperature range of 100°C to 139°C , which was consistent with the calculated weight loss of 15.51%. This weight loss was ascribed to the continuous breakdown and loss of 2CO . The next stage's decomposition takes place between 384°C and 814°C , when the projected weight loss of 24.41 percent and the observed weight loss of 24.37% are almost identical. This weight loss is correlated with continual decomposition and 2CO_2 loss. At 835°C , the residual product eventually transforms into CdMnO (cadmium manganese oxide) and up to 900°C , the compound is stable. There is a close match between the calculated residue weight of 55.56% and the actual residue weight of 55.52%. This demonstrates that cadmium manganese is present in the developed crystal [19-20].

Fig.3. TGA curve of cadmium manganese oxalate

Table 1. TGA data of cadmium manganese oxalate crystal

Stage	Temperature range ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Observed % Wt. loss	Calculate % Wt. loss	Loss of Molecule
1.	56 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	4.20	4.90	H ₂ O
2.	100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 139 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	15.83	15.51	2CO
3.	384 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 814 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	24.41	24.37	2CO ₂

B. DIFFERENTIAL THERMAL ANALYSIS (DTA)

The loss of molecule can be determined by using DTA analysis. DTA Spectrum for gel grown cadmium manganese oxalate crystal is shown in figure 4 and collected DTA data from this curve is tabulated in the table 2. According to DTA Curve in nitrogen which observed that the grown crystal shows three endothermic peaks. In the first stage an endothermic peak observed due to loss bulk of water of crystallization at 139 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the second stage, which is endothermic in nature and results from the oxidation of anhydrous cadmium manganese oxide, occurs at 393 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The decomposition of cadmium manganese oxalate is shown by the last endothermic peak at 597 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The endothermic peak in the TGA curve represents the whole weight loss of the water molecule under DTA treatment.

Fig.4. DTA curve of cadmium manganese oxalate.

Table 2. DTA data of cadmium manganese oxalate

Stage	Peak Record ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Peak Height (%)	Nature	ΔH (J/g)
1.	139 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	-68.69%	Endothermic	-127.012
2.	393 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	-14.68%	Endothermic	-105.489
3.	597 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	-1.693%	Endothermic	-9.992

C. DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALORIMETER (DSC)

Cadmium manganese oxalate crystal powder weighing 13.00 mg was taken out for DSC examination. DSC was conducted at KBCNMU, Jalgaon. The growing crystal's DSC examination was captured between 30°C to 300°C. The figure 5 represented DSC curve for cadmium manganese oxalate crystal. In good agreement with the DTA curve, the DSC curve verified the presence of an endothermic dip peak at 112°C, which leads to the creation of cadmium manganese oxide. Enthalpy change, or heat of transition, of 543 J/g was recorded in the temperature range of 90°C to 170°C.

Fig.5. DSC curve of cadmium manganese oxalate

D. PHOTOLUMINESCENCE SPECTROSCOPY (PL)

To observed optical properties of grown crystal by using Photoluminescence Spectroscopy which is carried out at Crysta Peak Solution Lab, Pune. Figure 6 displays the photoluminescence spectrum of ambient temperature cadmium manganese oxalate crystals. When activated, the emission spectra mostly include peaks at 312nm, 364nm, 466nm, and 540nm. Violet emission is represented by the low intensity peak at 364nm, where photon energy is 3.40eV [21]. Cyan emission is detected at 466nm [22], with a strong peak that indicates energy of 2.66eV. The green emission, which is the greatest intensity peak, has been identified at 540nm [23]. The energy of this emission peak is 2.296eV. It implies that the obstacle to two carboxyl groups spinning around the central C-C bond is quite low [24]. The fluorescence properties of grown manganese oxalate crystals demonstrate its superiority for optical applications [25].

Table 3. The PL spectrum for cadmium manganese oxalate crystals

Sr. No.	Wavelength (nm)	Emission	Photon Energy (eV)
1.	312	Violet	3.97
2.	364	Violet	3.40
3.	466	Cyan	2.66
4.	540	Green	2.29

Fig. 6. Emission spectrum of cadmium manganese oxalate

IV. CONCLUSION

- The single diffusion technique in agar-agar gel was used to effectively create a single crystal of cadmium manganese oxalate crystals.
- TGA analysis shows that the water of crystallization in the compound and built crystal is stable at temperatures up to 50⁰C.
- The presence of three endothermic peaks was examined by DTA.
- The grown crystal's enthalpy change transition is measured by DSC.
- The achieved cadmium oxalate crystal emits violet, cyan, and green emissions that indicate the fluorescent feature, according to photoluminescence spectroscopy.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The principal of S.G.P. Arts, Commerce and Science College, Sakri is acknowledged by the authors for providing laboratory facilities. We also appreciate the characterization facilities provided by Mr. Satish Bagal, CRYSTA PEAK SOLUTION LAB Pune, National Chemical Laboratory, Pune, and K.B.C.N.M.U. Jalgaon. For this insightful conversation on chemical reactions and other topics, thank you to Mr. Ganesh Patil and Mr. Deepak Patil of R.C. Patel Instituted, Shirpur.

REFERENCES

1. S. K. Bachhav, N. S. Patil, M. S. Kale and D. S. Bhavsar, "International Journal of Engineering Research and Application," Vol-4, PP.108-112, **2014**.
2. S. J. Nandre, S. J. Shitole and R. R. Ahire, "International Journal of Chemical and Physical Sci," Vol-3, PP.123-130, **2014**.
3. H. S. Pawar, S. J. Nandre, S. D. Chavan and R. R. Ahire, "Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research," Vol-8, PP.625-634, **2021**.
4. A. K. Patil, U. S. Jagtap and H. R. Talale, "International Journal of Basic and Applied Science," Vol-11, PP.108-113, **2022**.
5. S. K. Arora and T. Abraham, "Journal of Crystal Growth," Vol-52, PP.851-857, **1981**.
6. A. Pactor, "Kristall und Technik," Vol-12, PP.729-735, **1957**.
7. J. Dennis and H. K. Henisch, "Journal of Electro chemical society," Vol-114, PP.263-266, **1967**.
8. P. V. Dalal, "Indian Journal of Material Science," Vol-10, PP. 01-05, Article 682950, **2013**.
9. P. V. Dalal and K. B. Saraf, "Indian Academy of Science," Vol-34, PP.377- 381, **2011**.
10. Chauhan and Arrora, "Crystal Research and Technology," Vol-44, PP.189-196, **2009**.
11. B. B. Parekh, M. J. Joshi, and D. B. Vaidya, "Current Science," Vol-93, PP.373-378, **2007**.
12. M. Khunur, D. Misbah and P. P. Yunair, "Advances in Natural & Applied Sciences," Vol-5, PP.467, **2011**.
13. Y. Okamoto and W. Brenner, "Organic Semiconductors," Reinhold Publishing, Chapman & Hall, London, UK, **1964**.
14. V. Ramakrishnan, "Cryst. Res. Technol.," Vol-24, PP.513-516, **1989**.
15. Yanes, A. Lopez, C. T. Stockel, J. F. Peraza and M. E. Torres, "Journal of Materials Science," Vol-31, PP. 2683-2686, **1996**.
16. S. J. Joshi, K. P. Tank, B. B. Prakash and M. J. Joshi, "Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry," Vol-112, PP.761-766, **2012**.
17. A. S. Ganavi, N. Jaganath, K. P. Nagaraja, D. D'Souza and P. S. Rohith, "E-ISBN: 978-1-68576-4326," Vol-6, PP.34-41, **2023**.
18. S. U. Patil and R. T. Chaudhari, "International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Application in Engineering," Vol-4, PP.5990-5995, **2016**.
19. B. P. Agrawal, K. P. Chauhan and M. M. Bhadbhade, "Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Physics," Vol - 37. PP. 395-398, **1999**.
20. B. Tyagi, "Ph.D. Thesis," Department of Physics, Sardar Patel University, Vidyanagar, India, **2002**.
21. T. Vijayakumari, C. M. Padma and C. K. Mahadevan, "Journal of Engineering Research and Application," Vol- 4, PP. 47-52, **2014**.
22. D. K. Sawant, H. M. Patil, D. S. Bhavsar, J. H. Patil and K. D. Girase, "Archives of Physics Research," Vol-2, PP.67-73, **2011**.
23. D. K. Sawant, H. M. Patil, D. S. Bhavsar, J. H. Patil and K. D. Girase, "Pelagia Research Library," Vol-2, PP.63-69, **2011**.
24. C. M. Earnet, "Anal. Chem.," Vol- 59, PP. 1471-1475, **1984**.
25. T. Karpagam and K. Balasubramanian, "International Journal of Scientific Research in Science, Engineering and technology," Vol- 4, PP. 731-737, **2018**.